

C4 Deer Season Late

Start of Block: Default Question Block

Q1 Are you 18 or older?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Are you 18 or older? = No

Q2 Looking at this map, did you hunt today in any of the national refuge sites shown in green or blue, or any of the state wildlife areas marked in black? If so, which one or which ones?

- Beehive Bend (489)
- Capay (490)
- Codora (509)
- Dead Man's Reach (491)
- Flynn (492)
- Foster Island (493)
- Heron Island (494)
- Jacinto (northern/Feds) (495)
- Jacinto (southern/State) (496)
- Llano Seco Island (1 or 2) (497)
- La Barranca (498)
- Mooney (499)
- Ord Bend (500)
- Phelan Island (501)
- Pine Creek Units (state/federal) (502)
- Rio Vista (503)

South Ord (504)

Sul Norte (505)

Todd Island (506)

Wilson Landing (507)

Did not hunt in any of these sites (508)

Page Break

Q5 What is your home zip code?

Q6 Including yourself, how many people in your group hunted at this site today? Only include yourself and people in the same car as you, even if your group is bigger than that.

Q3 When did you arrive at this site?

(Interviewer, please record with time, am/pm, and day, e.g., "5:30 pm yesterday" or "6:00 am today")

Q4 When are you leaving this site?

(Interviewer: in most cases this will be the current time; please record with time, day and am/pm, e.g., "3 pm today." If hunter will spend more time at this site BEFORE RETURNING HOME, please indicate the additional time to be spent, e.g., "leaving 10 am today, returning for 2 more hours this pm")

Q7 What animal were you mainly hunting for today?

- Deer (1)
 - Pig (2)
 - Something else (enter it here) (3)
-

Display This Question:

If What animal were you mainly hunting for today? = Deer

Q8 Did you apply for a premium deer tag this year? If so, were you successful?

- Did not apply for a premium tag (1)
 - Applied but did not receive one (2)
 - Applied and got one (3)
-

Q9 How many days of hunting will you do on this trip? Consider this trip as starting when you left home and finishing when you return home.

Q10 Was hunting the primary reason for this trip?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Q11 Rate the quality of the habitat at the site you hunted today (regardless of whether your hunt was successful or not).

- Excellent (1)
 - Above average (2)
 - Average (3)
 - Below average (4)
 - Poor (5)
-

Q12 How many days in the last 12 months did you hunt at this site?

Q13 How many days in the next 12 months do you expect to hunt at this site?

Q14 How many years have you been hunting?

Q15 Sex:

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
-

Q16 In a few months, our research team is conducting a more in-depth survey about hunting that will take into account more of your opinions about hunting. We would like to ask you to

participate in this voluntary on-line survey. If you agree, we will follow up with you with an email asking you to participate in our longer survey later this year. That longer survey will take 10 to 20 minutes and will ask you additional questions related to your hunting experiences.

Are you willing to consider participating in the follow-up survey?

- Yes (1)
- Maybe (2)
- No (4)

Display This Question:

If In a few months, our research team is conducting a more in-depth survey about hunting that will t...
= Yes

Or In a few months, our research team is conducting a more in-depth survey about hunting that will t...
= Maybe

Q17 Can you please provide your email address so that we can send you the follow-up survey?
It will not be shared with anyone else and we will delete it after the follow-up survey is done.

Page Break

Q18 (Interviewer: record the site where the survey was taken.)

- Red Bluff Boat Launch (8)
- Mill Creek Park Boat Launch (1)
- Woodson Bridge Boat Launch (2)
- Irvine Finch Boat Launch (5)
- Ord Bend Boat Launch (3)
- Butte City Boat Launch (4)
- Sul Norte (6)
- Capay (7)

Q19 (Interviewer: use this space to record unusual occurrences/deviations from protocol, if any.)

Q20 (Interviewer: enter your name)

- Virginia (1)
- Liam (2)
- Zach (3)
- Cayle (4)
- Devin (5)
- Mike (6)
- Ruby (7)
- Chloe (9)
- Olivia (10)
- Marie (11)
- Weston (12)
- Richelle (13)

End of Block: Default Question Block
